

ELIXIR

Interoperability

Platform

2024-26

Work Plan

Abstract

The Interoperability Platform's mission has evolved beyond technical and semantic interoperability, responding to changing needs and life sciences standards. It has already created an ecosystem uniting expertise and information. Aligned with ELIXIR's priorities, it introduced peer-reviewed Recommended Interoperability Resources, established the ELIXIR Knowledge Hub, and fostered recognition of Research Data Management (RDM). Now it is transitioning to a sustainable framework for enabling real-world data integration and reuse by promoting and supporting interoperability, data management and FAIR principles. The strategy centres on "The 3 Ps": Products, Processes, and Practices. Products entail mapping and coordinating FAIR resources, minimising duplication, and enhancing user experience. Processes align products with user needs, ELIXIR Nodes, and global partners. Practices convert insights into actionable guidance, empowering users through the connection and use of diverse resources. These initiatives reinforce the Platform's dedication to interoperability, data stewardship, and efficient resource utilisation. Aligned with Open Science and FAIR principles, they cement the role of ELIXIR in the EOSC ecosystem.

This document shows the work plan version as approved by the ELIXIR Board in November 2023.

About this document

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Contents

Abstract	1
About this document	2
Authors	2
Acknowledgements	2
Contact	2
Copyright notice:	2
1. Objectives and relation to the Scientific Programme	4
2. Partnership	7
3. Work Package descriptions	9
Work Package 1 - Management and Coordination	9
Work Package 2 - Growing the FAIR-enabling portfolio of products	11
Work Package 3 - Standardising processes for FAIR data management	14
Work Package 4 - Establishing best practices for interoperable data management and use	19
Table of Deliverables and Milestones	23
Appendix B: Partner information	26

1. Objectives and relation to the Scientific Programme

The Interoperability Platform's mission to help people and machines to discover, access, integrate and analyse biological data has evolved since its inception; now going well beyond purely technical and semantic interoperability. This reflects its response to changing community needs and the creation of numerous standards initiatives across the life sciences. The Platform has successfully created an ecosystem of products and information, bringing together people and expertise. It is now maturing into a sustainable framework to promote and support wide-reaching efforts to solve challenges in the areas of identifiers, discoverability, ontologies and ontology services, file formats, metadata, and vocabularies, as well as APIs and workflows. It has also aligned its priorities with other parts of ELIXIR, such as the Data Platform, Communities and ELIXIR-led Projects, promoting the FAIR principles — Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable data.

To establish trust and aid sustainability of key resources, the Platform successfully delivered the Recommended Interoperability Resources (RIRs) peer-review scheme. It has also created the basis of the ELIXIR Knowledge Hub to develop and disseminate content on RDM know-how, and best practices, sign-posting key ELIXIR resources on the ELIXIR homepage. The FAIR-enabling activities of the Interoperability Platform, along with key projects like CONVERGE and FAIRplus have strengthened the recognition of Research Data Management (RDM) as a discipline in its own right, which has led to the creation of the ELIXIR RDM Community. This Community will be instrumental in this new phase of the Platform, in order to share, co-create, and reuse resources, tools, services and guidance to achieve greater real-world impact.

Building on these successes, the Interoperability Platform now looks to the next Programme with a clear vision, delineated by three interdependent areas (designated “The 3 Ps”): mature Products that enable FAIRification and responsible RDM, specific Processes that use (or need) Products, and broader Practices that enable a user to succeed.

Products: Resource Mapping, Coordination and Development

Analyse the landscape of FAIR-enabling products within ELIXIR, including services, standards, and other relevant components. Procedures to categorise and assess these products will be redefined or reshaped to streamline the portfolio and improve transparency. Parallel efforts will align and coordinate the long term sustainability of RDM resources, placing RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook at the core of an ecosystem that includes links to key resources like DSW and FAIRsharing. This activity strives to minimise duplication of effort, capitalising on synergies among resources, improving connectivity, and enhancing user experience and navigation. The overall goal is to provide a comprehensive and context-aware collection of FAIR-enabling and RDM-supportive products, within the broader context of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) framework.

Processes: Understanding User Needs and Promoting Alignment

Develop a common framework for the application of the aforementioned Products to support FAIRification of data and services across ELIXIR Nodes, Communities, and Projects, while also aligning with EOSC and global partners. This involves curating a library of interoperability stories (case studies), and will further ongoing efforts to standardise templates for outlining requirements and the resources needed to fulfil them. Gaps in the existing portfolio will be identified and

addressed through proactive engagement with stakeholders, including the EOSC Focus Group to ensure alignment with EOSC efforts.

Practices: Enabling Users

Convert knowledge gathered into actionable content, including guidance materials based on the interoperability stories. These should empower users to navigate and successfully utilise the diverse range of resources within the portfolio. Compiling these materials will include efforts to identify issues related to interoperability during data analysis and integration, as well as compute model compatibility. In parallel, existing sources of training materials, such as TeSS, will be assessed for relevance to the practices defined here. The evaluation will also consider how ELIXIR resources lie within the EOSC landscape and the shared vision for open and collaborative research.

In conclusion, these strategic initiatives underscore the ELIXIR Interoperability Platform's commitment to advancing interoperability, data stewardship, and efficient resource utilisation within the life sciences community. Its objectives align well with the European Commission's commitment to Open Science and the Platform's commitment to the FAIR principles and broader ELIXIR strategy, continuing to place ELIXIR in a key position within the EOSC ecosystem.

- SCIENCE PRIORITY - Enable scientists to access and analyse life science data**
 - S1 Cellular and molecular research
 - S2 Biodiversity, food security and pathogens
 - S3 Human data translational research

- TECHNOLOGY PRIORITY - Deliver services to support federated data management and analytics in life science**
 - T1 Research data management and data sharing
 - T2 Reproducible analytics and infrastructure
 - T3 Federated service delivery

- NODE PRIORITY - Equip ELIXIR Nodes for successful long-term operations**
 - N1 Node operations
 - N2 National research & open science policy alignment
 - N3 Industry and Innovation
 - N4 Impact and long-term sustainability

- PEOPLE PRIORITY - Develop people and capacity to benefit science and society**
 - P1 Use of ELIXIR services
 - P2 Management and operational staff
 - P3 Technical and scientific staff
 - P4 A diverse people network

Box 1. The primary strategic priorities and ambitions of the ELIXIR Scientific Programme 2024-2028 addressed by this project.

2. Partnership

Contributors to the work programme are listed in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Overview of involved institutions. Leads highlighted in **bold**.

Node	Institution	Abbreviation
EBI	European Molecular Biology Laboratory - European Bioinformatics Institute	EBI-EMBL
NL	Maastricht University	NL-MAAS
UK	University of Oxford	UK-UNIOXF
BE	Vlaams Instituut voor Biotechnologie (Flemish Institute for Biotechnology)	BE-VIB
CH	Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics	CH-SIB
CZ	Ústav organické chemie a biochemie AV ČR (Institute of Organic Chemistry and Biochemistry of the Czech Academy of Sciences)	CZ-IOCB
DE	Forschungszentrum Jülich (Jülich Research Center)	DE-FZJU
ELIXIR	ELIXIR Hub	ELIXIR-HUB
ES	Centre for Genomic Regulation	ES-CRG
UK	Imperial College London	UK-IMPL
UK	University of Manchester	UK-UNIMAN
UK	Quadram Institute	UK-QUADRAM
IT	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (National Research Council)	IT-CNR
IT	Università degli Studi di Padova (University of Padua)	IT-UNIPD
LU	Luxembourg National Data Service	LU-LNDS
LU	University of Luxembourg	LU-UNILU
NO	University of Oslo	NO-UIO
SE	Uppsala University	SE-UU
SI	Univerza v Ljubljani (University of Ljubljana)	SI-UNILJU

3. Work Package descriptions

Work Package 1 - Management and Coordination

WP 1	Lead Partner: UK-UNIOXF, EMBL-EBI, NL-MAAS
	Start month - End month: M01-M36
WP Partnership	
UK-UNIOXF - Susanna-Assunta Sansone	
EBI-EMBL - Tony Burdett	
NL-MAAS - Chris Evelo	
ELIXIR-HUB - Fabio Liberante (Coordinator); Clare Garrard	
Objectives	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate communication and collaboration among Platform members by <u>chairing monthly coordination calls</u>. • Coordinate the scientific agenda for the <u>annual Platform face-to-face meeting</u>. • Oversee the implementation of the Platform Work Plan to <u>ensure objectives are met</u> within the designated time frame. • Provide <u>reporting and progress updates</u> to ELIXIR governance bodies and stakeholders, where necessary, to foster transparency and accountability. • Regularly <u>review Platform strategy</u> to identify areas for improvement and propose necessary adjustments for enhanced efficiency and effectiveness. • Establish <u>communication channels with other ELIXIR Platforms</u> to ensure alignment and knowledge sharing • Participate in <u>joint-platform activities</u> to leverage collective expertise and resources. • Actively <u>engage with external partners</u> and organisations to seek collaboration and resource-sharing opportunities to enhance Platform capabilities and impact. • Where appropriate, <u>pursue additional avenues of funding and support</u>, including industry engagement, to boost sustainability. • Contribute to the broader impact of the Platform, by <u>aligning with the ELIXIR Programme and other Research Infrastructures</u> and initiatives, such as EOSC. • Communicate Platform activities by <u>engaging with ELIXIR Communities</u> and research communities in general. • <u>Represent the Platform in external contexts</u> and strategic partnerships. • Coordinate and contribute to <u>drafting and finalisation of Platform Work Plan</u> for remainder of 2024-2028 Programme 	

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution
D1.1	Year 1 Annual Report 2024 inc. F2F	UK-UNIOXF
D1.2	Year 2 Annual Report 2025 inc. F2F	EMBL-EBI
D1.3	End Report	NL-MAAS
D1.4	Final draft of revised Platform Work Plan for M36+	UK-UNIOXF
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution
M1.1	Completion and/or reassessment of WP2/3/4 objectives anticipated within previous year	UK-UNIOXF EMBL-EBI NL-MAAS
M1.2	Completion and/or reassessment of WP2/3/4 objectives anticipated within previous year	UK-UNIOXF EMBL-EBI NL-MAAS
M1.3	Completion and/or reassessment of WP2/3/4 objectives anticipated within previous year	UK-UNIOXF EMBL-EBI NL-MAAS
M1.4	Representation of Platform at at least 1 International Conference	UK-UNIOXF EMBL-EBI NL-MAAS

Work Package 2 - Growing the FAIR-enabling portfolio of products

WP 2	Lead Partner: LU-LNDS - Danielle Welter
	Start month- End month: M01-M36
WP Partnership	
CH-SIB - Vassilios Ioannidis (Activity 1 co-lead + operations)	
CZ-IOCB - Marek Suchánek (Activity 2 co-lead)	
UK-UNIMAN - Munazah Andrabi (Activity 1 co-lead)	
UK-UNIOXF - Allyson Lister (Activity 2 co-lead)	
LU-LNDS - Danielle Welter (Lead)	
BE-VIB - Bert Droesbeke (Activity 1 operations)	
UK-UNIOXF - Philippe Rocca-Serra	
NL-MAAS - Tooba Abbassi-Daloi	
NO-UIO - Nazeefa Fatima	
BE-VIB - Flora D'Anna	
DE-FZJU - Nils Hoffmann	
UK-UNIOXF - Susanna Sansone (ExCo rep. for this WP)	
<p>Objectives (Activity 1):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Align and coordinate the development of the RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Minimise duplication of efforts and maximise synergies between all resources ○ Optimise user experience, navigation and use ○ Continue to place the resources in the wider context of other FAIR-enabling products ● Map out the landscape of FAIR-enabling products, including services and standards, within ELIXIR <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Identify gaps in the current portfolio and proactively engage with other stakeholders within ELIXIR to address them ○ Redefine/reshape the current RIRs procedures to form the portfolio of FAIR-enabling products ○ Deliver guiding materials for users to easily and effectively navigate the wide range of resources within the portfolio 	

Description of Work

Activity 1: Coordination of the RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook in the wider context of the RDM ecosystem

Leads: Vassilios Ioannidis (CH), Munazah Andrabi (UK).

Contributors: Bert Droesbeke (BE), Philippe Rocca-Serra (UK), Tooba Abbassi-Daloi (NL), Danielle Welter (LU), Nazeefa Fatima (NO), Flora D'Anna (BE) (M1-M36)

The aim of this Activity is to formalise the coordination between the RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook to: (i) help their developers with growth, synchronisation and sustainability of the resources; (ii) better serve the ELIXIR and wider user community with complementary and comprehensive coverage; and (iii) engage efficiently with the RDM and other ELIXIR Communities, as well as external collaborators. Specifically, in this Activity we will bring together their respective editorial boards to:

- Define an aligned strategic vision across the two resources
- Further develop the technical and operational alignments currently in place
- Identify gaps/new content from a range of avenues, including outcomes from WP2 Activity 2, WP3 and 4, as well as ELIXIR Communities and Focus Groups
- Coordinate the addition of new content in alignment with the resources' remits and the shared strategic vision
- Continue to ensure cross-links between the two resources, and to others such as FAIRsharing, DSW, and bio.tools, where relevant
- Organise focus groups, joint hackathons, and contentathons to add guidelines and recipes on topics of strategic relevance to ELIXIR RDM and other Communities

Activity 2: Establish portfolio of endorsed FAIR-enabling services and standards

Leads: Allyson Lister (UK), Marek Suchánek (CZ).

Contributors: Danielle Welter (LU), Nazeefa Fatima (NO), Nils Hoffmann (DE) (M1-M36)

The aim of this Activity is to formalise and endorse a portfolio of services and standards that support and enable FAIRness, leveraging Activities from WP3 and WP4, as well as reviewing the impact to date of the RIRs, in order to identify revisions and improvements required to this process. Specifically, in this Activity, we will:

- Survey and analyse the landscape of FAIR-enabling services and standards used across the ELIXIR RDM and other Communities and Nodes
- Identify core services and standards, as well as gaps in the ELIXIR portfolio, working closely with WP3 and informed by the 'interoperability stories'
- Review and update the RIRs procedures, categorization, and evaluation criteria for services, based on experiences to date (does RIR serve its purpose?)
- Create 'live' representations of standards and their profiles in FAIRsharing, to track their status and maximise their use by data resources
- Formalise the ELIXIR portfolio and how it is disseminated to the user, enhancing relevant pages of the ELIXIR website

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution
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D2.1	Report on the operations of the RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook collaborations, including new content resulting from joint activities <i>Vassilios Ioannidis, Munazah Andrabi</i>	CH-SIB
D2.2	User guide to ELIXIR FAIR service portfolio, including FAIRsharing factsheets, and improved ELIXIR web pages <i>Danielle Welter</i>	LU-LNDS
D2.3	Reviewed inclusion and evaluation criteria, as well as the general qualification process, for ELIXIR-endorsed FAIR-enabling services <i>Marek Suchánek</i>	CZ-IOCB
D2.4	FAIRsharing collection of ELIXIR-recommended standards showcasing interoperability of databases and the standards they implement <i>Allyson Lister</i>	UK-UNIOXF
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution
M2.1	Mission statement of the joint/coordinating board, including definition of processes, practices and operations <i>Vassilios Ioannidis</i>	CH-SIB
M2.2	Roadmap for the strategic alignment of RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook in the context of the wider RDM community, including planning for joint contentathons <i>Munazah Andrabi</i>	UK-UNIMAN
M2.3	Cross WP sessions to showcase user stories, document landscape and identify current gaps in FAIR-enabling service portfolio <i>Nazeefa Fatima</i>	NO-UIO
M2.4	Review and roadmap of RIR process - including analysis of the value of the RIR "badge" and users' feedback <i>Marek Suchánek</i>	CZ-IOCB

Work Package 3 - Standardising processes for FAIR data management

WP 3	Lead Partners: CH-SIB - Vassilios Ioannidis SE-UU - Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström
	Start month- End month: M01-M36
WP Partnership	
SE-UU - Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström	
UK-UNIMAN - Nick Juty	
IT-UNIPD - Ivan Mičetić	
CH-SIB - Vassilios Ioannidis	
EBI-EMBL - Wei Kheng Teh	
UK-IMPL - Ibrahim Emam	
NL-MAAS - Tooba Abbassi-Daloi	
NO-UIO - Nazeefa Fatima	
ES-CRG - Julia Ponomarenko	
UK-UNIOXF - Philippe Rocca-Serra	
NO-UIO - Sveinung Gundersen	
SI-UNILJU - Brane Leskošek	
DE-FZJU - Nils Hoffmann	
SI-UNILJU - Polonca Ferk	
<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define the components of a common framework for interoperability that will support FAIRification of data and services across ELIXIR Nodes, Communities and Projects and promote alignment with EOSC and ELIXIR's global partners • Curate a comprehensive and well-organised library of interoperability case studies and use cases that will serve as input to initiatives across ELIXIR Platforms, and as examples including lessons learned to a wide range of stakeholders across ELIXIR 	
<p>Description of work:</p> <p>This work package will identify, assess, refine and test processes, resources and best practices in FAIR data management, and consolidate them into a common FAIRification framework.</p>	

Ultimately, this framework will be used as a reference to which FAIR implementations across ELIXIR Nodes, Communities and Projects can be realigned. Of primary interest are the processes and activities that mobilise people and resources to achieve interoperability across the different aspects of FAIR data management. The common FAIRification framework will describe the requirements, recommendations, processes and resources that drive successful FAIR implementations to deliver the objectives of the ELIXIR Interoperability Platform.

The work will be organised under two activities, each focusing on one of the two objectives. The first activity focuses on defining the common FAIRification framework while the second activity focuses on collecting a comprehensive library of 'Interoperability stories' that illustrate how the framework manifests in case studies and use cases across ELIXIR. Our approach in developing those two activities will adopt an iterative approach to engage stakeholders in hands-on workshops to solve interoperability challenges while incrementally developing and refining the two flagship deliverables—the framework and the library of interoperability stories—and working towards a shared report describing the relevance and efficacy of the deliverables.

A minimum of 6 “bring your own data” (BYOD) workshops will be organised with participants from ELIXIR Communities. Community BYOD workshops will recruit cross-functional participants, including scientific experts from within ELIXIR communities, data stewards and FAIR experts—especially members of the interoperability platform and the RDM community—and will run throughout the programme. BYOD workshops will support both activities in this work package, helping to validate, and refine the common FAIRification framework and create new interoperability stories. Following each workshop, the outcomes and lessons learned will be reported back to the respective activities to serve as input to the development of the next version and validation of the deliverables. In addition, the activities will also suggest improvements and opportunities for re-alignment of the framework components used in the workshops, such as the maturity assessment component (FAIR Dataset Maturity model) and FAIRification goal development component.

Activity 1: Converge communities around the use of a common FAIRification framework

Leads: Nick Juty (UK), Ibrahim Emam (UK)

Contributors: Tooba Abbassi-Daloi (NL), Philippe Rocca-Serra (UK), Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (SE), Vassilios Ioannidis (CH), Sveinung Gundersen (NO), Wei Kheng Teh (EBI)

Duration: M1-M36

Achieving true interoperability remains a challenging goal. Data stewards across ELIXIR routinely define new, *ad hoc* approaches and workflows in an attempt to create FAIR data within their nodes and communities, despite the good work that has been done over many years to create resources supporting interoperability. This activity will lay down the architecture of a common framework that brings together all necessary components that will enable ELIXIR data stewards to approach FAIRification of data and services with a systematic and scalable process, with a focus on Interoperability as a common FAIRification goal to serve different stakeholders of the ELIXIR Interoperability Platform (EIP).

The work will initially build and improve on the FAIR in action [FAIRification framework](#) and supporting initiatives such as the [FAIR Dataset Maturity model](#), FAIRification goal development,

and FAIR Cookbook in alignment with the EIP [FAIR Services Architecture Framework](#). The aim of this work is to formalise a practical solution-based framework for FAIRification tasks in an iterative approach based on feedback from work in WP2 (landscaping) and guided by the 'interoperability stories' in WP3, Activity 2. This framework will be validated practically and refined over the course of the work plan through the proposed series of BYOD workshops.

Plan of work:

- Analyse a selection of FAIRification and interoperability frameworks that are well-documented and familiar to the WP contributors to converge on an initial list of requirements and a first minimal draft framework
- Define a minimal common reporting structure for the workshop events to collect experiences to guide the future revisions and validation of the framework
- Iteratively select/define use cases to focus on for each of the workshops to maximise the utility of the framework and demonstrate its efficacy across EIP stakeholders—arranging the workshops in coordination with Activity 2
- Define a candidate release of the framework and call for EIP members to review and provide feedback for final revisions and validation.
- Finalise the framework and alignment with Activity 2.

Outcomes:

- A conceptual model defining common requirements, recommendations, processes and resources that drive successful FAIR implementations to deliver the interoperability objectives of the EIP
- A common FAIRification framework with demonstrated utility in supporting FAIRification workshops that can be adopted across EIP stakeholders and the wider RDM community to solve interoperability challenges

Activity 2: Collect a comprehensive library of 'Interoperability stories' from across ELIXIR

Leads: Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (SE), Ivan Mičetić (IT)

Contributors: Nick Juty (UK), Brane Leskošek (SI), Nazeefa Fatima (NO), Vassilios Ioannidis (CH), Ibrahim Emam (UK), Julia Ponomarenko (ES), Nils Hoffmann (DE)

Duration: M1-M36

The [previous work programme](#) demonstrated how 'Interoperability stories' could be used to provide mappings from impact, through use cases and case studies, to tools, processes and best practices, and maturity assessments. This activity will extend the number of stories covered to represent the stakeholders of the EIP and adopt a common structure with a sufficient level of detail to support the development and validation of the common FAIRification framework of Activity 1. The work will begin by analysing the current collection of 'interoperability stories' to identify recurring concepts and use cases of relevance to the framework of Activity 1 and to define an initial list of gaps with regards to the types of tools and use cases covered. The work will involve soliciting new and more detailed 'interoperability stories' by reaching out to ELIXIR Projects, Nodes and Communities and a selection of relevant EOSC initiatives and other external partners to request and support their contributions. The structure and content will be refined as

the framework evolves and the work will shift focus towards consolidating the stories into a library of case studies and use cases, and soliciting feedback to ensure that the library can be used as input to future initiatives and stakeholders across ELIXIR.

Plan of work:

- Identify recurring concepts and use cases of relevance to the framework of Activity 1 in EIP’s current collection of ‘interoperability stories’ and define a list of gaps with regards to the types of tools and use cases covered
- Define a minimal common reporting structure for the workshop events to facilitate contributions of new and more detailed ‘interoperability stories’ and to assess their utility for EIP stakeholders
- Iteratively identify gaps and opportunities to improve the structure of the library to support each of the workshops and to avoid unintentional overlaps with existing resources (such as in the RDMkit / FAIR Cookbook)—arranging the workshops in coordination with Activity 1
- Define a candidate release of the library and proposed path to integrating the ‘interoperability stories’ in RDMkit, FAIR Cookbook and the wider RDM ecosystem followed by a call for EIP members to review and provide feedback for revision and validation
- Design and open a call for contributions of ‘interoperability stories’ from ELIXIR Projects, Nodes and Communities and a selection of relevant EOSC initiatives and other external partners
- Finalise the library and alignment with Activity 1 and extract a summary of the FAIR enabling technologies in use while highlighting emerging tools and use cases

Outcomes:

- A common structure to organise and report ‘interoperability stories’ with demonstrated utility in supporting FAIRification workshops to solve interoperability challenges that can be adopted across EIP stakeholders
- A collection of ‘interoperability stories’ with wide representation across tools, use cases and stakeholders that can be used as input to future initiatives that will shape the ELIXIR Platforms and to provide examples and lessons-learned to a wider range of stakeholders across ELIXIR, also serving as guidelines for newcomers and new use cases
- A summary of opportunities to improve content for the RDMkit, the FAIR Cookbook and the wider RDM ecosystem based on the collection of ‘interoperability stories’
- An overview of FAIR enabling technologies and use cases represented across the collection of ‘interoperability stories’ that showcase current and emerging practices across ELIXIR that can guide future activities in the ELIXIR ecosystem of resources

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution
D3.1	Common FAIRification Framework. <i>Ibrahim Emam</i>	UK-IMPL

D3.2	Comprehensive library of 'Interoperability stories' with an overview of the FAIR enabling technologies and use cases represented. <i>Ivan Mičetić</i>	IT-UNIPD
D3.3	Report on the utility of the FAIRification Framework and library of 'Interoperability stories'. <i>Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström</i>	SE-UU
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution
M3.1	First FAIRification workshop announced with a tentative schedule for future workshops. <i>Nick Juty</i>	UK-UNIMAN
M3.2	Draft FAIRification framework distributed to stakeholders based on the input from the first FAIRification workshop with a scheme to manage revisions and future versions throughout the programme. <i>Nick Juty</i>	UK-UNIMAN
M3.3	Draft library of 'interoperability stories' fully aligned with the FAIRification framework with a prioritised list of gaps to address during the second half of the programme. <i>Ivan Mičetić</i>	IT-UNIPD
M3.4	List of driver initiatives and stakeholders committed to participate in the final rounds of validation and refinement of the deliverables. <i>Vassilios Ioannidis</i>	CH-SIB

Work Package 4 - Establishing best practices for interoperable data management and use

WP 4	Lead Partners: NL-MAAS - Tooba Abbassi-Daloi ES-CRG - Antonio Hermoso Pulido
	Start month- End month: M01-M36
WP Partnership	
NL-MAAS - Tooba Abbassi-Daloi	
ES-CRG - Antonio Hermoso Pulido	
UK-QUADRAM - Falk Hildebrand	
IT-CNR - Flavio Licciulli	
LU-UNILU - Marek Ostaszewski	
NL-MAAS - Elena Domínguez-Romero	
UK-UNIOXF - Allyson Lister	
NL-MAAS - Denise Slenter	
NO-UIO - Federico Bianchini	
NO-UIO - Sveinung Gundersen	
CH-SIB - Tarcisio Mendes de Farias	
UK-UNIMAN - Nick Juty	
NL-MAAS - Chris Evelo	
NO-UIO - Korbinian Michael Bösl	
Objectives	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate and draw attention to issues of interoperability (positive or negative) that occur during actual data analysis or integration of different types of data, and also in relation to data and compute models. • Conduct a use case-driven inventory of individual steps and complete workflows, and the resources supporting these processes, to identify any missing components. • Evaluate resources with training materials for their actual content and links among these resources (think TeSS, Galaxy, WorkflowHub) and between them and bio.tools. 	

- Assess both the content of training materials provided by resources such as TeSS, Galaxy and WorkflowHub, and the connections between those same resources and to others such as bio.tools

Description of Work

Activity 1: Engage RDM and analysis experts to identify services, tools, workflows, and their usage, using data from deposition databases and example FAIR data

Leads: Tooba Abbassi-Dalooi (NL), Flavio Licciulli (IT)

Contributors: Marek Ostaszewski (LU), Falk Hildebrand (UK), Allyson Lister (UK), Elena Domínguez-Romero (NL), Nick Juty (UK), Sveinung Gundersen (NO) (M1 - M36)

The aim of this activity is to evaluate the interoperability approaches, workflows and tools used for data analysis, integration and reuse. By doing so, we aim to enhance the reusability of datasets and metadata that are being shared in selected (OMICS) deposition databases. To achieve this, we plan to establish connections between these deposited datasets and various other types of data using interoperable tools and workflows. This will also help identify existing methods we can better support and promote across ELIXIR and beyond. To accomplish this, we will:

- Identify and select deposited datasets in ELIXIR deposition databases (specifically using OmicsDI, BioSamples, BioStudies in the process and then ArrayExpress, ENA, PRIDE, MetaboLights and possibly EGA for the actual datasets) and evaluate their reusability.
- Choose a number of example data reuse approaches to examine, and potentially improve their data requirements. Examples mentioned, but not yet chosen, were disease maps (used in many communities), ordinary differential equation based physiological kinetic models (as used in toxicology and systems biology communities), and whole genome metabolic maps (used in microbiome, food and nutrition, metabolomics). Collate use cases (stories) from Activity 2 WP3 that are relevant to different ELIXIR communities based on these approaches
- Utilise the workflows collected from Activity 2 WP3 to link and integrate the chosen datasets.
- Identify interoperability resources (tools and code libraries) for resources relevant during data reuse and combining identical, related, or hierarchically related entities. Examples are ontology lookup (e.g. OLS, BioPortal) and mapping (e.g. OxO, Zooma), database identifier resolution (e.g. identifiers.org and BridgeDb), chemical structure resolution and (sub)structure mapping (e.g. CDK, ontologies), executable transformations and models (modularity solutions, e.g. Omnipy, conversions to and from SBML and to LaTeX), the whole set of sequence similarity tools (e.g. CleanUp). Evaluate relevant standards (e.g. SSSOM, SBML).
- Evaluate the practical interoperability of the deposited datasets (i.e. can it be combined with other data or reused in analysis and modelling approaches).
- Evaluate a mechanism for post deposition enrichment of annotation of data in the deposition databases and an associated validation procedure.
- Create a list of recommendations for dataset requirements to ensure successful interoperability when reusing datasets. These recommendations may be generic and

applicable to multiple workflows or specific to a particular interoperability task. Creation of FAIRsharing ELIXIR Community Champions to ensure enriched ELIXIR content and highlight recommendations of FAIR-enabling ELIXIR resources in WP2 and help with the profile of resources using FAIR data.

Activity 2: Outreach, dissemination & training

Lead: Antonio Hermoso Pulido (ES)

Contributors: Denise Slenter (NL), Tooba Abbassi-Daloi (NL), Allyson Lister (UK), Federico Bianchini (NO) (M1 - M36)

Based on the use cases of Activity 1, make an inventory of existing training material for workflows, molecular data analysis procedures and tutorials for specific analytical and interoperable tools relevant for data reuse and integration. In this regard, we will especially focus on interoperability resources to support finding relations and mappings needed during data reuse in the fields also covered in Activity 1 (i.e. text to ontologies, (standards for) ontological terms mappings, database identifiers and their resolvability, chemical structure relationships, hierarchical relationships (e.g. SNPs to genes to processes or gene expression to proteins to tissue localization). Our work plan will be:

- Decide on the best places to make these available (e.g. TeSS, Galaxy, FAIRsharing and/or WorkflowHub).
- Improve training material metadata via ontology terms (e.g., from EDAM, already implemented in TeSS, and [terms4FAIRskills](#), a terminology for skills already implemented in [ELIXIR training material](#)) and explore the interlinking between the different training resources (e.g., by using Bioschemas). Wherever possible, provide approaches for the reuse of these training materials and explore mechanisms for assessing their validity over time (enabling graceful degradation).
- Work with the bio.tools and FAIRsharing platforms on better, ideally automated, links between training material and the involved tools, aiming at reducing annotation needs and increasing findability. Whenever possible, use the same technology approach for providing links among the actual training repositories.
- Identify specific gaps in existing training material on data reuse, aligned to the findings of the other Activities in the Interoperability Platform. Work with the Training Platform and engage relevant ELIXIR Communities to fill them. Generate guidelines of good data reuse practices, so they can be included in existing and upcoming materials.

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution
D4.1	Inventory of reuse approaches and interoperability resources needed based on the 3 use cases <i>Tooba Abbassi-Daloi</i>	NL-MAAS
D4.2	Overview (e.g., spreadsheet) documenting dissemination efforts and the ways to connect them <i>Antonio Hermoso Pulido</i>	ES-CRG

D4.3	Establishment of ELIXIR Node representatives in the FAIRsharing Community Champions Programme <i>Allyson Lister</i>	UK-UNIOXF
D4.4	Short report on use case outcomes and impacts <i>Flavio Licciulli</i>	IT-CNR
D4.5	Recommendations document on data reuse for guiding training efforts <i>Federico Bianchini</i>	NO-UIO
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution
M4.1	Procedures for data reuse use cases agreed, and data and workflows to evaluate selected <i>Tooba Abbassi-Dalooi</i>	NL-MAAS
M4.2	Outreach, dissemination and training platforms to evaluate and use selected. Links between them evaluated and method for inventories of content selected and presented to use cases. <i>Antonio Hermoso Pulido</i>	ES-CRG

Table of Deliverables and Milestones

Deliverable / Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M2.1	Mission statement of the joint/coordinating board, including definition of processes, practices and operations <i>Vassilios Ioannidis</i>	CH-SIB	6
M3.1	First FAIRification workshop announced with a tentative schedule for future workshops. <i>Nick Juty</i>	UK-UNIMAN	6
D1.1	Year 1 Annual Report 2024 inc. F2F	UK-UNIOXF	12
M1.1	Completion and/or reassessment of WP2/3/4 objectives anticipated within previous year	UK-UNIOXF EMBL-EBI NL-MAAS	12
M2.2	Roadmap for the strategic alignment of RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook in the context of the wider RDM community, including planning for joint contentathons <i>Munazah Andrabi</i>	UK-UNIMAN	12
M3.2	Draft FAIRification framework distributed to stakeholders based on the input from the first FAIRification workshop with a scheme to manage revisions and future versions throughout the programme. <i>Nick Juty</i>	UK-UNIMAN	12
M4.1	Procedures for data reuse use cases agreed, and data and workflows to evaluate selected <i>Tooba Abbassi-Daloi</i>	NL-MAAS	12
M4.2	Outreach, dissemination and training platforms to evaluate and use selected. Links between them evaluated and method for inventories of content selected and presented to use cases. <i>Antonio Hermoso Pulido</i>	ES-CRG	12
D4.3	Establishment of ELIXIR Node representatives in the FAIRsharing Community Champions Programme <i>Allyson Lister</i>	UK-UNIOXF	18
M1.4	Representation of Platform at at least 1 International Conference	UK-UNIOXF EMBL-EBI NL-MAAS	18
M2.4	Review and roadmap of RIR process - including analysis of the value of the RIR "badge" and users' feedback <i>Marek Suchánek</i>	CZ-IOCB	18
M3.3	Draft library of 'interoperability stories' fully aligned with the FAIRification framework with a prioritised list of	IT-UNIPD	18

	gaps to address during the second half of the programme. <i>Ivan Mičetić</i>		
D1.2	Year 2 Annual Report 2025 inc. F2F	EBI-EMBL	24
D2.2	User guide to ELIXIR FAIR service portfolio, including FAIRsharing factsheets, and improved ELIXIR web pages <i>Danielle Welter</i>	LU-LNDS	24
M1.2	Completion and/or reassessment of WP2/3/4 objectives anticipated within previous year	UK-UNIOXF EMBL-EBI NL-MAAS	24
M2.3	Cross WP sessions to showcase user stories, document landscape and identify current gaps in FAIR-enabling service portfolio <i>Nazeefa Fatima</i>	NO-UIO	24
M3.4	List of driver initiatives and stakeholders committed to participate in the final rounds of validation and refinement of the deliverables. <i>Vassilios Ioannidis</i>	CH-SIB	24
D1.4	Final draft of revised Platform Work Plan for M36+	UK-UNIOXF EMBL-EBI NL-MAAS	30
D2.3	Reviewed inclusion and evaluation criteria, as well as the general qualification process, for ELIXIR-endorsed FAIR-enabling services <i>Marek Suchánek</i>	CZ-IOCB	30
D3.1	Common FAIRification Framework. <i>Ibrahim Emam</i>	UK-IMPL	30
D3.2	Comprehensive library of 'Interoperability stories' with an overview of the FAIR enabling technologies and use cases represented. <i>Ivan Mičetić</i>	IT-UNIPD	30
D4.1	Inventory of reuse approaches and interoperability resources needed based on the 3 use cases <i>Tooba Abbassi-Daloi</i>	NL-MAAS	30
D4.2	Overview (e.g., spreadsheet) documenting dissemination efforts and the ways to connect them <i>Antonio Hermoso Pulido</i>	ES-CRG	30
D1.3	Year 3 Annual Report 2026 inc. F2F	NL-MAAS	36
D2.1	Report on the operations of the RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook collaborations, including new content resulting from joint activities <i>Vassilios Ioannidis, Munazah Andrabi</i>	CH-SIB & UK-UNIMAN	36
D2.4	FAIRsharing collection of ELIXIR-recommended standards showcasing interoperability of databases and the standards they implement <i>Allyson Lister</i>	UK-UNIOXF	36

D3.3	Report on the utility of the FAIRification Framework and library of 'Interoperability stories'. <i>Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström</i>	SE-UU	36
D4.4	Short report on use case outcomes and impacts <i>Flavio Licciulli</i>	IT-CNR	36
D4.5	Recommendations document on data reuse for guiding training efforts <i>Federico Bianchini</i>	NO-UIO	36
M1.3	Completion and/or reassessment of WP2/3/4 objectives anticipated within previous year	UK-UNIOXF EMBL-EBI NL-MAAS	36

Appendix B: Partner information

Table Partner information

Institution	Contact Name
BE-VIB	Bert Droesbeke
BE-VIB	Flora D'Anna
CH-SIB	Tarcisio Mendes de Farias
CH-SIB	Vassilios Ioannidis
CZ-IOCB	Marek Suchánek
DE-FZJU	Nils Hoffmann
EBI-EMBL	Tony Burdett
EBI-EMBL	Wei Kheng Teh
ELIXIR-HUB	Physilia Chua
ELIXIR-HUB	Fabio Liberante
ELIXIR-HUB	Clare Garrard
ES-CRG	Antonio Hermoso Pulido
ES-CRG	Julia Ponomarenko
UK-IMPL	Ibrahim Emam
UK-QUADRAM	Falk Hildebrand
UK-UNIMAN	Munazah Andrabi
UK-UNIMAN	Nick Juty
UK-UNIOXF	Allyson Lister
UK-UNIOXF	Philippe Rocca-Serra
UK-UNIOXF	Susanna Sansone
IT-CNR	Flavio Licciulli
IT-UNIPD	Ivan Mičetić
LU-LNDS	Danielle Welter
LU-UNILU	Marek Ostaszewski
NL-MAAS	Chris Evelo
NL-MAAS	Denise Slenter
NL-MAAS	Elena Domínguez-Romero
NL-MAAS	Tooba Abbassi-Daloi
NO-UIO	Federico Bianchini

NO-UIO	Korbinian Michael Bösl
NO-UIO	Nazeefa Fatima
NO-UIO	Sveinung Gundersen
SE-UU	Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström
SI-UNILJU	Brane Leskošek
SI-UNILJU	Polonca Ferk